

CA20104 – Network on evidence-based physical activity in old age (PhysAgeNet)

Deliverable D1.2

Systematic reviews using the database D1.1 submitted for publication related to PA interventions and EBM

Contributors

Working Group 1: Implementation and development of standards from evidence-based medicine (EBM)

1.3.1. Chronic exercise and depressive symptoms

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Description of the activities of the subgroup:

The subgroup “Chronic exercise and depressive symptoms” has met 10 times since the summer of 2022. The slides presented during the meetings were posted on the Riga Stradins University Teams space. The subgroup already completed the following operations: (1) search of randomized controlled trials examining the effect of chronic exercise on depressive symptoms in older adults in several databases (30,765 articles found), (2) uploading the references of these 30,765 articles in Rayyan, (3) removal of duplicates (10,347 duplicates removed), (4) selection of studies based on abstracts by pairs of reviewers (19,845 articles excluded), (5) selection of studies based on full-text by pairs of reviewers (411 articles excluded), (6) preparation of the questionnaire to extract the data on REDCap, (7) extraction of a sample of selected data and storage of these data in REDCap by pairs of reviewers, (8) conducting the meta-analysis on Comprehensive meta-analysis v4. The first results are presented in section 3. The review protocol has been registered on PROSPERO [CRD42022361418] and accepted for publication in PLOS One. The next stages to finish the systematic review and meta-analysis are described in the two Gantt charts hereafter. The submission of the final article is planned in January 2025.

Timeline of the activities for 2024 and 2025:

Tasks	2024											
	Feb	Mar	April	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	
Solving the conflicts	█											
Quality assessment of the RCTs (ROB2)	█	█										
Statistical analyses		█										
Writing a report for the COST action		█										
Presentation of the results in Kaunas			█									
Continuing extraction: EF and BCT				█	█	█						
Analyzing secondary outcomes					█	█	█	█				
Writing the article(s)								█	█	█	█	

Tasks	2025								
	Jan	Feb	Mar	April	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep
Submission of the main article		█							
Writing of secondary articles			█	█	█	█	█	█	█
Reviewing process of the main article				█	█	█	█	█	█
Working on deliverables D.1.4 and D.1.5				█	█	█	█	█	█

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2. Results of the meta-analysis on the chronic effects of exercise on overall depression level in older adults

As mentioned in section 1.3.1, the protocol of the present meta-analysis has been registered on PROSPERO [CRD42022361418] and accepted for publication in PLOS One (doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0297348). We present hereafter the main results of the meta-analysis that will be published in a indexed international journal.

2.1. General results

The analysis is based on 162 effect sizes (129 studies). A table with the references of the 129 studies is provided in appendix 1. The effect size index is the standardized difference in means (Cohen’s d). Computations were carried out using Comprehensive Meta-Analysis Version 4 (Borenstein et. al., 2022).

2.1.1. Statistical model

The random-effects model was employed for the analysis. The studies in the analysis are assumed to be a random sample from a universe of potential studies, and this analysis will be used to make an inference to that universe (Borenstein, 2019; Borenstein et al., 2010; Borenstein et al., 2021; Hedges & Vevea, 1998; Higgins & Thomas, 2019).

2.1.2. What is the mean effect size?

The mean effect size of the effect of chronic exercise on overall depression level is -0,675 with a 95% confidence interval of -0,779 to -0,572 (see Figure 1). The mean effect size in the universe of comparable studies could fall anywhere in this interval. This moderate effect size indicates that chronic exercise reduces the overall depression level by 0.675 standard deviation.

Figure 1: Caterpillar plot of the 162 effect sizes included in the meta-analysis

The Z-value tests the null hypothesis that the mean effect size is zero. The Z-value is -12,776 with $p < 0,001$. Using a criterion alpha of 0,050, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that in the universe of populations comparable to those in the analysis, the mean effect size is not precisely zero.

2.1.3. The Q-test for heterogeneity

The Q-statistic provides a test of the null hypothesis that all studies in the analysis share a common effect size. If all studies shared the same true effect size, the expected value of Q would be equal to the degrees of freedom (the number of studies minus 1). The Q-value is 1143,668 with 161 degrees of freedom and $p < 0,001$. Using a criterion alpha of 0,100, we can reject the null hypothesis that the true effect size is the same in all these studies.

2.1.4. The I-squared statistic

The I-squared statistic is 86%, which tells us that some 86% of the variance in observed effects reflects variance in true effects rather than sampling error.

2.1.5. Tau-squared and tau

Tau-squared, the variance of true effect sizes, is 0,348 in d units. Tau, the standard deviation of true effect sizes, is 0,590 in d units.

2.1.6. The prediction interval

If we assume that the true effects are normally distributed (in d units), we can estimate that the prediction interval is -1,845 to 0,495 (see Figure 2). The true effect size in 95% of all comparable populations falls in this interval (Borenstein, 2019, 2020; Borenstein et al., 2021; Borenstein et al., 2017; DerSimonian & Laird, 1986, 2015; Higgins, 2008; Higgins & Thompson, 2002; Higgins et al., 2003; Higgins & Thomas, 2019; IntHout et al., 2016).

Figure 2: Prediction interval of true effects and confidence interval of the mean effect size.

2.2. Moderator analyses

2.2.1. Exercise characteristics

2.2.1.1. Moderator: Type of exercise

Rationale: Numerous recent meta-analyses have been conducted to investigate the differential effects of various types of exercise on overall depression levels in healthy older adults (Miller et al., 2020), and in older adults with Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) (Liu et al., 2023). For older adults, both with and without MCI, it was found that mind-body exercises were most beneficial in reducing depression levels (Liu et al., 2023; Miller et al., 2020). However, resistance, aerobic, and multicomponent exercises also proved effective, albeit slightly less so, still demonstrating moderate effect sizes. Therefore, we hypothesize that all the types of exercise included in our study are effective in reducing depressive symptoms, though through different mechanisms. Mind-body exercises, which combine low-intensity muscular activities (such as flexibility or balance training) with an internally guided focus fostering a self-contemplative state of mind, are hypothesized to be particularly effective.

Results: A subgroup analysis, including 162 effect sizes, revealed that the type of exercise significantly explained the heterogeneity of the effect sizes, $Q(6) = 19.830$, $p = .003$. The efficacy of different types of exercise in reducing overall depression levels can be ranked in the following order: (1) exergames ($n = 6$; $SMD = -1.705$; $95\% CI = [-2.789, -0.622]$), (2) resistance exercises ($n = 27$; $SMD = -0.973$; $95\% CI = [-1.244, -0.702]$), (3) mind-body exercises ($n = 33$; $SMD = -0.733$; $95\% CI = [-0.979, -0.568]$), (4) aerobic exercises ($n = 30$; $SMD = -0.625$; $95\% CI = [-0.947, -0.304]$), (6) Coordinative exercises ($n = 3$; $SMD = -0.529$; $95\% CI = [-0.965, -0.093]$), (7) Multi-component exercises ($n = 55$; $SMD = -0.460$; $95\% CI = [-0.602, -0.318]$), (8) Dance exercises ($n = 8$; $SMD = -0.378$; $95\% CI = [-0.087, -0.069]$).

Discussion: Contrary to our hypothesis and the results of the meta-analyses by Miller et al. (2020) and Liu et al. (2023), we did not find mind-body exercise to be the most effective type of exercise. However, similar to those studies, the effect sizes between mind-body exercises, aerobic exercise, and strength exercises were comparable (ranging from -0.97 to -0.63). Interestingly, for exergames, a type not included in the meta-analyses by Miller et al. (2020) and Liu et al. (2023), we found them to be the most effective, with an effect size of -1.71. This beneficial effect aligns with the findings of Yen & Chui (2021), who reported large effects of exergames on depressive outcomes in older adults. It might be suggested that exergames benefit the mental health of older adults by not only including cognitive and physical exercises but also promoting social interactions with other actors such as players, therapists, avatars, and animals. However, the within-study heterogeneity was quite high. Therefore, further research is needed to more specifically identify which aspects of exergames moderate the beneficial effect on depression in older adults.

2.2.1.2. Moderator: Intensity of exercise

Rationale: The level of exercise intensity can significantly affect the type and extent of psychological and physiological adaptation to exercise training and can impact the human body's internal metabolic and cardiovascular stress (Mann, Lamberts, & Lambert, 2013; Xie et al., 2021). Regarding the anti-depressant properties of exercise, recent research has

shown that the intensity of exercise plays a significant role in the anti-depressant effect of various types of exercise, such as strength training, resistance training, yoga, and tai chi (Nebiker et al., 2018; Noetel et al., 2024). For instance, increasing the intensity of exercise by 10% has been found to have a notable positive effect on depression levels (Nebiker et al., 2018). Therefore, we hypothesized that the higher the exercise intensity, the larger the effect of exercise training intervention on overall depression levels.

Results: There was a significant effect of the intensity of exercise on the effect size: $Q(2) = 7.180$; $p = .028$. The exercises with a vigorous intensity or higher ($n = 25$; $SMD = -1.138$; $95\% CI = [-1.535, -0.740]$) led to a larger effect size than moderate ($n = 80$; $SMD = -0.570$; $95\% CI = [-0.707, -0.432]$) and light intensity exercises ($n = 57$; $SMD = -0.676$; $95\% CI = [-0.842, -0.509]$). The difference between the mean effect size of light and moderate intensity exercises: $Q(1) = 0.922$; $p = .337$.

Discussion: The results of the current analysis revealed that exercise training prescriptors, such as exercise intensity, can significantly impact the level of amelioration of overall depression symptoms in older people. The results of this study support recent meta-analyses on the relationship between exercise training and depression in younger populations that reported that high-intensity exercise interventions are more effective in reducing depression compared to moderate or light-intensity ones (Nebiker et al., 2018; Noetel et al., 2024). In conclusion, exercise intensity has a moderating effect on overall depression levels in older people, with high intensities being more effective than moderate and light intensities.

2.2.1.3. Moderator: Duration of exercise sessions

Rationale: Based on a previous meta-analysis examining the effects of chronic exercise on cognitive aging (Colcombe & Kramer, 2003), we can hypothesize that RCTs that use moderate duration sessions lead to larger effect sizes because it could be considered that the optimal duration to maintain a high level of engagement of older participants is between 30 and 60 minutes. RCTs using shorter or longer intervention sessions could be considered as less optimal and leading to smaller effect sizes. Short session RCTs would not be sufficiently long to induce large and enduring changes, whereas long session RCTs would introduce acute fatigue effects. To perform this analysis, we distinguished four categories of studies: (1) short duration sessions (< 30 min), (2) moderate duration sessions (30 < duration < 60 min), (3) long duration session (> 60 min), (4) session duration not specified.

Results: A subgroup analysis, including 162 effect sizes, revealed that the duration of exercise sessions did not significantly explain the heterogeneity of the effect sizes, $Q(3) = 2.562$, $p = .464$. There was no significant difference between the four categories of RCTs: RCTs using short duration sessions ($n = 16$; mean duration = 18.79 min; $SMD = -0.434$; $95\% CI = [-0.767, -0.101]$), RCTs using moderate duration sessions ($n = 90$; mean duration = 48.95 min; $SMD = -0.660$; $95\% CI = [-0.794, -0.525]$), RCTs using long duration sessions ($n = 13$; mean duration = 95.36 min; $SMD = -0.687$; $95\% CI = [-0.985, -0.389]$), RCTs that did not specify the duration of sessions ($n = 18$; $SMD = -0.482$; $95\% CI = [-0.778, -0.186]$).

Discussion: Contrary to our hypothesis, the duration of the exercise sessions did not influence the size of the effect of chronic exercise on overall depression level. However, it can be noticed that moderate durations are the most used by researchers (75%).

2.2.1.4. Moderator: Frequency of exercise sessions

Rationale: The meta-analysis of Sanders et al. (2019) suggested that the more frequent the exercise sessions were, the greater the benefit in cognitive function in older adults. Using the same logic, we can hypothesize that the more frequent the exercise sessions, the larger the reduction in overall depression level.

Results: The meta-regression, including 145 effect sizes, indicated that the frequency of exercise sessions did not explain the heterogeneity of the effect sizes of chronic exercises on overall depression level ($\beta = -0.008$, $R^2 = .00$, $p = .795$).

Discussion: Contrary to our expectations, we did not find a relationship between the frequency of exercise sessions and the effect size of the interventions. This moderator should not be considered alone, but certainly in combination with session duration and duration of the intervention.

2.2.1.5. Moderator: Total duration of the intervention (in weeks)

Rationale: Recent systematic reviews and meta-analyses are inconclusive regarding the effect of intervention duration on participants' depressive episodes (Kandola et al., 2019; Singh et al., 2023). It is noted that the effectiveness of physical activity interventions may decrease with increasing duration of interventions. Longer duration interventions had smaller effects if compare with mid- and short duration, but the longest duration interventions still had positive effects (Singh et al., 2023). Within clinical populations interventions lasting 10–16 weeks lead to greater effects than interventions lasting 4–9 weeks (Lee et al., 2022; Rethorst et al., 2009; Singh et al., 2023). However, in the general population, interventions lasting 4–9 weeks resulted in significantly larger effects than interventions lasting 17–26 weeks, and interventions lasting 10–16 weeks also produced significantly larger effects than interventions lasting 16–26 weeks and more than 26 weeks (Rethorst et al., 2009). Considering the results of research, we hypothesized that the duration of the intervention is positively correlated with the beneficial effects of exercise until a certain duration.

Results: The meta-regression, including 155 effect sizes, indicated a marginal relationship between the duration and the effect size of chronic exercises on overall depression level ($\beta = -0.0001$, $R^2 = .00$, $p = .05456$). This indicated that the longer the duration of the intervention in the studies, the larger the beneficial effects of chronic exercise on the overall depression level (see Figure 3). This result matches with that found by Yen et al. (2021) who observed that the total intervention duration had a significant effect on depressive outcomes, the longest duration leading to a greater efficiency against depressive outcomes ($\beta = -0.255$; $p = 0.11$).

Figure 3: regression line between standardized difference in means of level of depression as a function of duration of intervention in the RCT.

Discussion: Our meta-regression did not find a significant relationship between the duration of intervention and the effect of chronic exercise on overall depression level. This result is inconsistent with earlier studies (Craft & Landers, 1998; North et al., 1990) according to which longer intervention resulted in larger decreases in depression scores, while also being consistent with more recent work on the lack of a linear relationship (Lee et al., 2022; Rethorst et al., 2009; Singh et al., 2023). One of the possible mechanisms explaining this effect may be the insufficient duration of the interventions, as well as the number of such interventions. Most exercise interventions for depression are around 16 weeks, and this period may only be sufficient to induce functional connectivity changes (Rethorst et al., 2009). Exercise must last for at least six months to induce structural changes (for example, in hippocampal volume), longer exercise interventions may induce structural changes that have a more pronounced impact on depressive symptoms. Also exercise produces several functional, but transient changes in neuroplasticity, such as elevations in BDNF circulation, improvements in cardiorespiratory fitness are necessary for more lasting structural changes and cognitive benefits (Kandola et al., 2019).

2.2.1.6. Moderator: Volume of the intervention

Volume = Session frequency (NO sessions per week) * Session duration (in min) * Program duration (in weeks)

Rationale: Among the number of studies that investigate the protective role of physical activity on depression, results are largely heterogeneous (Noetel et al., 2024; Singh et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2019). Among the findings is the ascertainment of the fact of a positive effect of physical activity on reducing the severity and symptoms of depression (Singh et al., 2023). Other studies have examined physical activity across different parameters, including frequency, duration, and volume, and have produced more complex results. Some findings

indicated that individuals who participated in physical activity with greater frequency were less likely to be depressed; some researches that lower frequency or PA with a lower volume is a protective factor (Wang et al., 2019). We hypothesize that chronic exercise interventions differ in their efficacy in reducing overall depression severity in older adults across interventions with different exercise characteristics (i.e., frequency of exercise sessions, duration of exercise session, and duration of intervention).

Results: The meta-regression, including 141 effect sizes, indicated a linear relationship between the volume of intervention and the effect size of chronic exercise on overall depression level ($\beta = -0.0001$, $R^2 = .00$, $p = .04$). This indicated that the larger the volume of the intervention in the studies, the larger the effects of chronic exercise on the overall depression level (see Figure 4).

Discussion: Our meta-regression indicated a significant relationship between intervention volume and the effect of chronic exercise on overall depression level. This result is consistent with some previous studies (Wang et al., 2019). At the same time the lack of consensus on this issue indicates that the relationship between physical activity and depression may be dependent on cultural and socio-demographic indicators (Olanrewaju et al., 2016), and also confirms the multidimensional nature of exercise training that consists of intensity, frequency, and duration of intervention (Falck et al., 2016).

Figure 4: regression line between standardized difference in means of level of depression as a function of volume of intervention in the RCT.

2.2.1.7. Moderator: Cognitive demand of exercises

Rationale: Two categories of exercise have been distinguished based on the cognitive load of the exercises included in the exercise programs. On the one hand, high cognitive demanding exercises include balance exercises, coordinative exercises, mind-body exercises, exergames and cognitive tasks. On the other hand, low cognitive demanding exercises include aerobic exercises and resistance exercises. Based on previous works, we know that depressed

patients meet difficulties to perform effortful tasks and engage in effortful activities (Horne et al., 2021; Vinckier et al., 2022). Consequently, if the exercise program requires too much effort, depressed patients will not adhere to this program. We can then make the hypothesis that exercise programs including high cognitive demanding tasks lead to smaller effects size in the reduction of overall depression than programs including low cognitive demanding tasks.

Results: A subgroup analysis, including 162 effect sizes, revealed that the cognitive demand of exercises involved in exercises programs significantly explained the heterogeneity of the effect sizes, $Q(1) = 4.193, p = .041$. RCTs including exercises with a high cognitive demand ($n = 66$; $SMD = -0.812$; 95 % $CI = [-0.987, -0.636]$) led to significantly larger effect sizes than RCTs including exercises with a low cognitive demand ($n = 96$; $SMD = -0.585$; 95 % $CI = [-0.712, -0.458]$).

Discussion: Contrary to our initial hypothesis, interventions including exercises with a high cognitive demand led to larger effect sizes than interventions including exercises with a low cognitive demand. This result is coherent with the literature on the effects of chronic exercise on cognitive aging showing that dual-task exercises combining physical and cognitive tasks simultaneously are more effective in improving global cognition, memory function and executive functions than exercise alone (Zhao et al., 2022). Consequently, it could be recommended to include exercises with a high cognitive demand in RCTs that aim to reduce depression, such as exergames or mind-body exercises.

2.2.1.8. Moderator: Social interactions during exercise sessions

Rationale: For this moderator, we used four categories: “group-based” interventions, “individual-based” interventions, “mixed” interventions combining group-based and individual-based interventions and “not specified” for studies that did not report this information. Two previous meta-analyses showed that group-based interventions are more effective than individual-based interventions to improve mental health and reduce Parkinson’s symptoms in the elderly (Mortazavi et al., 2013; Mitsui et al., 2021). This effect could be explained by the fact that exercising in a group setting leads to higher adherence (Carron et al., 2006; Farrance et al., 2016). Based on these results, we made the hypothesis that group-based and mixed interventions lead to larger effect size than individual-based interventions.

Results: A subgroup analysis, including 162 effect sizes, revealed that the social interactions during exercise sessions significantly explained the heterogeneity of the effect sizes, $Q(3) = 21.670, p < .001$. Subsequent pairwise comparisons showed that group-based RCTs ($n = 100$; $SMD = -0.741$; 95 % $CI = [-0.875, -0.608]$) led to a larger effect size than individual-based RCTs ($n = 41$; $SMD = -0.354$; 95 % $CI = [-0.494, -0.214]$): $Q(1) = 15.458, p < .001$. There was no significant difference between the mean effect size for group-based and mixed-based RCTs ($n = 13$; $SMD = -0.869$; 95 % $CI = [-1.392, -0.347]$): $Q(1) = 0.216, p = .642$. The mean effect size for RCTs not reporting information about social interactions is the largest ($n = 8$; $SMD = -1.605$; 95 % $CI = [-2.520, -0.690]$) and only significantly different from that of individual-based RCTs. For this last category, the number of RCTs is very small ($n = 8$) certainly leading to an overestimation of the mean effect size. All the other comparisons were not significant.

Discussion: The results of the present meta-analysis confirm the superiority of group-based interventions over individual-based interventions to reduce overall depression.

2.2.1.9. Moderator: Autonomy of participants during exercise sessions

Rationale: It is assumed that supervised exercise programs (e.g., lab-based) lead to higher training adherence and better exercise performance quality compared to exercise programs conducted autonomously by participants (e.g., home-based). This might result in higher training intensity and a higher training volume, ultimately leading to greater exercise-related adaptations (see study on interventions to improve balance in older adults: Lacroix et al., 2017). Therefore, we hypothesize that RCTs incorporating supervised exercise interventions result in larger improvements in overall depression levels than those including autonomous interventions. For this moderator, we used four categories: “home-based” interventions, “supervised” interventions led by professionals, “mixed” interventions combining home-based and supervised interventions and “not specified” for studies that did not report this information.

Results: A subgroup analysis, including 162 effect sizes, revealed that the autonomy of participants significantly explained the heterogeneity of the effect sizes, $Q(3) = 13.283$; $p = .004$. Subsequent pairwise comparisons showed that RCTs including supervised exercise interventions ($n = 126$; $SMD = -0.742$; $95\% CI = [-0.864, -0.620]$) led to significantly larger effect sizes than RCTs including home-based autonomous exercise interventions ($n = 15$; $SMD = -0.250$; $95\% CI = [-0.488, -0.013]$); $Q(1) = 13.039$, $p < .001$. The RCTs combining home-based and supervised interventions led to an intermediate effect size ($n = 17$; $SMD = -0.742$; $95\% CI = [-0.864, -0.620]$) not significantly different from those of the two main other categories. All the other comparisons were not significant. We did not perform pairwise comparisons with the category “Not specified” because the number of RCTs was too small ($n = 2$).

Discussion: In line with our hypotheses, we found that supervised exercise interventions are more effective than autonomous exercise interventions in improving overall depression levels. Schuch et al. (2016) already analyzed this intervention characteristic in their meta-analysis. However, they only included one RCT that incorporated an autonomous component in its regimen. Thus, we are the first meta-analysis to analyze this intervention parameter comprehensively. These findings suggest that when using exercise as a treatment for depression, supervised interventions are recommended.

2.2.2. Population characteristics

2.2.2.1. Moderator: Mean age of the whole sample

Rationale: Continuous increase of depressive symptoms with rising age has been previously shown in older adults (Glaesmer et al., 2011). Previous meta-analyses have examined the effects of age as a moderator on the exercise-depression relationship giving contradictory results. While one study found an increasingly beneficial effect of exercise with increasing age (Bo et al., 2017), another study found opposite results with decreasing positive effects with increasing age (Klil-Drori et al., 2020), and a third study found no moderating effect of age (Rhyner & Watts, 2016). We hypothesized that the higher the age at baseline is, the larger the size of the effect of chronic exercise on depression will be. The possible mechanism could be that the increased prevalence of depressive symptoms in the advanced-aged population in

addition to the lower physical activity levels would lead to a greater effect of exercise on depression.

Results: A meta-regression, including 161 effect sizes, indicated a positive correlation between the mean age of the samples of participants and the effect of chronic exercise on overall depression level: $\beta = -0.0313$, $R^2 = .06$, $p < .001$. This indicated that the higher the mean age of the population included in the studies, the smaller the beneficial effects of chronic exercise on the overall depression level (see Figure 5).

Discussion: Contrary to our hypothesis, our meta-regression found a positive correlation between the mean age of the samples of participants and the effect of chronic exercise on overall depression level. This result aligns with the findings of a meta-analysis of Klil-Drori et al. (2020) which also showed decreasing positive effects with increasing age. Overall, these results suggest that the higher the mean age of the population, the smaller the beneficial effects of chronic exercise on the overall depression level are.

Figure 5: regression line between standardized differences in means of level of depression as a function of the mean age of the whole sample of participants included in the RCTs.

2.2.2.2. Moderator: Percentage of women in the sample of participants included in the RCT

Rationale: Numerous epidemiological studies have shown that the risk of experiencing a depressive episode throughout the lifespan is higher in women than in men (Girgus, Yang & Ferri, 2017; Poole & Jackowska, 2018). Moreover, other epidemiological studies have indicated that the relative risk for depression is larger in inactive women than in inactive men (e.g., Farmer et al., 1988), suggesting that women may be more responsive to the preventive effect of regular exercise on depression. Therefore, we hypothesized that the higher the percentage of females in the sample of participants included in the RCT, the larger the effect of chronic exercise on overall depression level.

Results: A meta-regression, including 120 effect sizes, indicated no significant correlation between the percentage of women and the effect of chronic exercise on overall depression level, $\beta = -0.005$, $R^2 = .000$, $p = .102$.

Discussion: Contrary to our expectations, our meta-regression did not find a significant relationship between the percentage of women in the sample of participants included in the RCT and the effect of chronic exercise on overall depression level. This result aligns with the findings of a meta-analysis of Schuch et al. (2016), comprising 6 RCTs, which also observed no significant correlation between the percentage of women in the included studies and the effect of chronic exercise on the overall depression level in older adults ($\beta = -0.017$, $p = 0.40$). Overall, these results suggest that the antidepressant effect of exercise is equally beneficial for both men and women.

2.2.2.3. Moderator: Type of population

Rationale. Seven types of population have been distinguished: participants with (1) neurodegenerative diseases (e.g., Alzheimer disease, Parkinson disease, dementia), (2) cardiovascular diseases (e.g., heart failures, strokes, hypertension), (3) other diseases (e.g., osteoarthritis, osteoporosis, diabetes, cancer), (4) depressive disorders (e.g., major depression, depressive symptoms), (5) cognitive impairments (e.g., mild cognitive impairment, cognitive frailty, major neurocognitive disorder), (6) other disabilities (e.g., visual impairment, frailty, hemodialysis, wheelchair) or (7) asymptomatic participants. Older adults included in this last category were not diagnosed with a specific disease, disorder, or disability and could include people with sleep complaints, pre-frailty, and/or high risk of falls. Older adults were considered as belonging to the fourth category “Depressive disorders” if and only if depression was diagnosed with the DSM (IV or V) diagnostic criteria. When participants had comorbidities, we only considered the disease, disorder or disability that justified the inclusion of the participants in the RCT. This analysis was conducted with an exploratory approach to see if certain populations are more responsive to exercise interventions in reducing overall depression level. The only hypothesis that could be made a priori is that populations diagnosed with depressive symptoms should show a larger effect size due to a larger window to observe the effect.

Results: A subgroup analysis, including 162 effect sizes, revealed that the type of exercise significantly explained the heterogeneity of the effect sizes, $Q(6) = 28.254$, $p < .001$. The responsiveness of the different types of the population to exercise programs in reducing overall depression levels can be ranked in the following order: (1) depressive disorders ($n = 25$; $SMD = -1.006$; $95\% CI = [-1.355, -0.658]$), (2) other diseases ($n = 14$; $SMD = -0.823$; $95\% CI = [-1.151, -0.495]$), (3) asymptomatic ($n = 60$, $SMD = -0.793$; $95\% CI = [-0.993, -0.593]$), (4) cognitive impairments ($n = 12$; $SMD = -0.572$; $95\% CI = [-0.772, -0.372]$), (5) neurodegenerative diseases ($n = 24$; $SMD = -0.467$; $95\% CI = [-0.700, -0.233]$), (6) other disabilities ($n = 12$; $SMD = -0.342$; $95\% CI = [-0.512, -0.172]$), (7) cardiovascular diseases ($n = 15$; $SMD = -0.293$; $95\% CI = [-0.480, -0.106]$).

Discussion: The results confirm that population diagnosed with depressive symptoms are more responsive to exercise programs leading to a reduction of overall depression level. It is surprising to notice that populations with cardiovascular disease showed the smallest effect size.

2.2.2.4. Moderator: Education level at baseline

Rationale: Several studies have demonstrated that the level of education is a risk factor for depression (Chlapecka et al., 2020; Domènech-Abella et al., 2018; Schlax et al., 2019). Higher education levels are associated with a low prevalence of depression than lower education levels (Hinata et al., 2021), suggesting that persons with higher education levels are more inclined towards regular exercise and its effect on depression. Therefore, we expect that the higher the level of education in the sample of participants included in the RCT, the larger the effect of chronic exercise on overall depression levels.

Results: A meta-regression, including 75 effect sizes, indicated no significant correlation between the level of education and the effect of chronic exercise on overall depression level, $\beta = -0.007$, $R^2 = .000$, $p = .734$.

Discussion: Contrary to our expectation, the level of education seems not to be a determinant of the reduction in overall depression induced by chronic exercise.

2.2.2.5. Moderator: Level of global cognition at baseline

Rationale: Recent studies have revealed that patients with cognitive disorders and depressive symptoms exhibit significant abnormalities in immune-inflammatory control, neurotransmitters, peripheral brain-derived neurotrophic factor levels, lipid metabolism, and protein homeostasis (Diniz et al., 2015). Therefore, physical exercise might help alleviate depressive symptoms in these patients by improving some of the aforementioned biological processes (Leng et al., 2018). Since participants with a higher level of global cognition at baseline may have fewer abnormalities in neurobiological functions, thereby having less potential for improvement, we hypothesize that the lower the global cognition at baseline, the greater the effect of chronic exercise on overall depression level.

Results: A meta-regression, including 53 effect sizes, indicated no significant correlation between the mean level of global cognition at baseline of the samples of participants and the effect of chronic exercise on overall depression level; $\beta = -0.0075$, $R^2 = .00$, $p = .560$.

Discussion: Contrary to our hypothesis, we found no relationship between the mean level of global cognition at baseline and the effects of chronic exercise on overall depression level. One explanation could be that a lower level of global cognition negatively impacts attendance rates, thereby nullifying the positive effects of the exercise.

2.2.2.6. Moderator: Functional capacity at baseline (handgrip strength + 6-min walk test)

Rationale: The relationship between functional capacity or physical fitness and the risk of having depressive symptoms in old age is well examined and documented (e.g., Arrieta et al., 2018; Brooks et al., 2018; Kong, Hong, & Kang, 2022). It has been found that poor lower body muscle strength is associated with greater odds of depressive episodes (Kong et al., 2022) and that the number of steps taken by older persons per day was negatively associated with the risk of depression (Arrieta et al., 2018). More specifically, reduced levels of handgrip strength are associated with greater self-reported depressive symptoms (Brooks et al., 2018), and a better performance at the six minutes walking test was correlated with a lower depression rate (Bae et al., 2023). Nevertheless, the role of functional capacity as a moderator of the effect of exercise on depression is yet to be empirically established. In a population-based cross-sectional study Kong et al., (2022) found that lower body muscle

strength was a moderator of the impact of insufficient (reported) physical activity on depression, in that poor strength was related to higher depressive symptoms in insufficiently active individuals. This led us to hypothesize that the effect of chronic exercise on overall depression level will be higher among individuals with higher functional capacity at baseline.

Results: A first meta-regression, including 25 effect sizes, indicated no significant correlation between the hand grip strength and the effect of chronic exercise on overall depression level, $\beta = -0.016$, $R^2 = .000$, $p = .607$. A second meta-regression, including 19 effect sizes, indicated no significant correlation between the 6-min walk test and the effect of chronic exercise on overall depression level, $\beta = -0.003$, $R^2 = .000$, $p = .328$.

Discussion: Contrary to our research hypotheses our meta-regression did not find a significant relationship between the hand grip strength, or the 6-min walk test and the effect of chronic exercise on overall depression level. The absence of a moderating effect in our meta regression could be attributed to various potential causes underlying differences in the baseline physical fitness. Different levels of fitness may result from physical, social, demographic or psychological factors (McPhee et al., 2016) which could vary in their moderating effect. Based on the results we conclude that baseline functional capacity is not a moderator of the general effect of chronic physical activity on depression.

2.2.3. Protocol characteristics

2.2.3.1. Moderator: Type of control group

Rationale: Based on the findings of several studies, larger window to observe a significant effect when comparing the treatment group with a passive control group (e.g., Northey et al., 2018; Ren et al., 2021). Therefore, we hypothesized that larger effect size will be observed when comparing the treatment group with a passive control group, than when comparing the treatment group with an active control group in RCT.

Results: A subgroup analysis, including 162 effect sizes, revealed that type of control group did not significantly explain the heterogeneity of the effect sizes, $Q(1) = 0.000$, $p = .995$. In other words, the type of control group does not significantly influence the effect size. RCTs with active control group did not led to a significantly different effect sizes than RCTs with passive control group.

Discussion: Contrary to our expectations, our sub-group analysis did not explain a significant effect on overall depression level. Exercise conditions that are strongly weighted on a single control comparison may erroneously inflate or deflate effect size estimates if there is no distinction made between multiple control conditions (Pagoto et al., 2013). It may be that the control conditions in our study were not separated into separate conditions. Thus, future studies should continue to take type of control group into account. Overall, these results suggest that the antidepressant effect of exercise is equally beneficial for both active and passive control group.

2.2.3.2. Moderator: Type of analysis

Rationale: Three types of statistical analysis have been considered. In RCTs using an intention-to-treat analysis, all participants, whatever the dropout rate and their adherence to the treatment, are included in the analysis to test the efficacy of the treatment. In this case, missing data were replaced by different techniques of imputation. In RCTs using a

complete-case analysis, the number of participants is the same at the beginning and at the end of the intervention for all the groups or the authors only analyzed data from participants who completed the study and had no missing data. Finally, in RCTs using a per-protocol analysis, only the participants who adhere to the treatment are included in the analysis to test the efficacy of the treatment. Most clinical researchers and statisticians agree that the primary analysis of data in a randomised controlled trial should compare patients according to the group to which they were randomly allocated, regardless of patients' compliance, crossover to other treatments, or withdrawal from the study. Such an analysis is referred to as an intention to treat analysis. Proponents argue that the intention to treat approach helps preserve prognostic balance in the study arms, limits inferences based on arbitrary or ad hoc sub-groups of patients in the trial, emphasizes greater accountability for all patients entered into the study and consequently minimizes the influence of withdrawals, non-compliers, and patients lost to follow up, is the most cautious approach and so minimizes type 1 error, and finally allows for the greatest generalizability (Fergusson et al., 2002). Critics say, however, that an intention to treat approach is too cautious and more susceptible to type II error (Sommer & Zeger, 1991; Rubin, 1998). Consequently, we can hypothesize that intention-to-treat analyses have the tendency to underestimate the effect size (type II error) and per-protocol analysis to overestimate the effect size (type I error).

Results: A subgroup analysis, including 162 effect sizes, revealed that the type of statistical analysis significantly explains the heterogeneity of the effect sizes, $Q(2) = 8.724, p = .013$. Pairwise comparisons revealed that RCTs using a complete-case analysis ($n = 119$; $SMD = -0.744$; $95\% CI = [-0.873, -0.615]$) led to a larger effect size than RCTs using an intention-to-treat analysis ($n = 32$; $SMD = -0.421$; $95\% CI = [-0.603, -0.238]$): $Q(1) = 8.009, p = .005$. RCTs using a per-protocol analysis ($n = 11$; $SMD = -0.851$; $95\% CI = [-1.339, -0.364]$) obtained the largest mean effect size as expected, but it was not significantly different from the mean effect size obtained with the two other types of analysis.

Discussion: Contrary to our hypothesis, we did not observe a significant difference between the effect sizes obtained in RCTs using an intention-to-treat analysis and those using a per-protocol analysis. In contrast, the RCTs using complete-case analysis, which were the most frequent category (73%), showed a larger effect size than RCTs using intention-to-treat analysis. Consequently, to have a clear idea of the efficacy of an exercise program it would be interesting to conduct the three analyses: one replacing missing values of people who dropped out (intention-to-treat analysis), one analyzing only participants with no missing value (complete-case analysis) and one analyzing only participants who adhere to the different interventions (per-protocol analysis).

2.2.3.3. Moderator: Study design

Rationale: Two study designs, or more precisely two different methods of randomization, have been distinguished. In the parallel-group design, each participant is randomly assigned to a group, and all participants receive (or do not receive) an intervention. In the cluster design, pre-existing groups of participants (e.g., villages, nursing homes) are randomly selected to receive (or not receive) an intervention. This analysis is exploratory and we have no a priori hypothesis concerning this moderator.

Results: A subgroup analysis, including 162 effect sizes, revealed that the study design did not significantly explain the heterogeneity of the effect sizes, $Q(1) = 0.082$, $p = .775$. In other words, the study design does not significantly influence the effect size. RCTs using a parallel-group design ($n = 148$; $SMD = -0.674$; $95\% CI = [-0.786, -0.562]$) did not lead to a significantly different effect size than RCTs using a cluster-design ($n = 14$; $SMD = -0.720$; $95\% CI = [-1.018, -0.422]$).

Discussion: The type of study design (parallel-group vs. cluster) does not seem to be an important determinant of the effect size of chronic exercise interventions on overall depression level. The parallel-group design remains the most used design in the research community (91%).

2.3. Conclusion

The first results of the present meta-analysis clearly showed that exercise-based interventions are effective to reduce overall depression level leading to a moderate effect size ($d = -0,675$). According to moderator analyses, the most effective exercise program should include exercises with the following characteristics: high cognitive demand (e.g., exergames or mind-body exercise), vigorous or high intensity, supervised group-based. In addition, interventions with a large volume of training are more effective than interventions with a lower volume. Concerning, the population more responsive to exercise interventions with the aim to reduce overall depression level, the moderator analyses suggest that the higher the age and depressive symptoms at baseline, the smaller the effect size; i.e., with aging, it is more and more difficult to reduce depression through exercise intervention. Based on this results, evidence-based recommendations will be formulated.

The present results will be shortly completed by several analyses: analysis of the interactions between pairs of moderators, analysis of the effect of the risk of bias on the effect size, analysis of the effect of publication bias on the effect size, analysis of the effect of chronic exercise on different symptoms of depression (e.g., apathy, fatigue, sleep).

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Appendix 1

#	Authors	Depression scale
1	Ahmed (2019)	GDS-30
2	Aibar-Almazan et al. (2019)	HADS
3	Albinet et al. (2016)	GDS-30
4	An et al. (2020)	GDS-30
5	Ansai & Rebelatto (2015)	GDS-15
6	Antunes et al. (2005)	GDS-30
7	Belza et al. (2002)	CESD-11
8	Bernard et al. (2015)	BDI
9	Bernardelli et al. (2019)	GDS-30
10	Bonura (2008), Bonura et al. (2014)	GDS-30
11	Bouaziz et al. (2019)	GADS-18
12	Brăilescu et al. (2017)	HAMD-17
13	Brenes et al. (2007)	HAMD-17 & GDS-15
14	Buman et al. (2011)	CESD-10
15	Casas-Herrero et al. (2022)	GDS-15
16	Chang et al. (2020)	BDI & HAMD-17
17	Chang et al. (2021)	GDS-15
18	Chen et al. (2008)	CESD-20
19	Chen et al. (2021)	GDS-15
20	Cheng et al. (2012)	GDS-15
21	Chin et al. (2022)	HADS & PHQ-9
22	Choi & Sohng (2018)	GDS-15
23	Chou et al. (2004)	CESD-20
24	Clegg et al. (2014)	GDS-15
25	Cordes et al. (2021)	CESD
26	Cugusi et al. (2015)	BDI-II
27	Deus et al. (2021)	BDI
28	Dong et al. (2013)	GDS-15
29	Eggermont et al. (2009)	GDS-30
30	Fakhari (2017)	BDI-II
31	Farzane & Koushkie Jahromi (2022)	HADS
32	Ferreira et al. (2015)	GDS
33	Flegal et al. (2007) / Oken et al. (2006)	CESD-10
34	Frih et al. (2017)	HADS
35	Furtado et al. (2021)	CESD-20
36	Gary et al. (2004), Gary (2006)	GDS-15
37	Gary et al. (2010)	HAMD-17
38	Ge et al. (2022)	GDS-30
39	Gleeson et al. (2017)	GDS-5
40	Haboush et al. (2006)	HAMD-17 & GDS-30
41	Hashimoto et al. (2015)	SDS
42	Hembree (2000)	BDI
43	Henskens et al. (2018)	CSDD

44	Hsu et al. (2016)	GDS-15
45	Irwin et al. (2014)	IDS-30
46	Jeong et al. (2019)	GDS-15
47	Jeong et al. (2021)	GDS-30
48	Jin et al. (2019)	GDS-15
49	Jolly et al. (2009)	HADS
50	Kerse et al. (2010)	GDS-15
51	Kim et al. (2019)	GDS-15
52	Kraiwong et al. (2021)	PHQ-9
53	Krawczyk et al. (2019)	MDI
54	Krishnamurthy & Telles (2007)	GDS-15
55	Lai et al. (2006)	GDS-15
56	Langoni et al. (2019)	GDS-15
57	Laredo-Aguilera et al. (2018)	GDS-15
58	Lee et al. (2013)	GDS-15
59	Lee et al. (2018)	BDI
60	Liao et al. (2018)	GDS-30
61	Lima et al. (2019)	HAMD-17
62	Lin et al. (2007)	GDS-15
63	Lin et al. (2020)	HADS
64	Lincoln et al. (2011)	GDS-30
65	Lippke et al. (2022)	CESD-20
66	Liu et al. (2018)	GDS-30
67	Ma et al. (2018)	CESD-10
68	Maci et al. (2012)	CSDD
69	Makizako et al. (2020)	GDS-15
70	Martínez et al. (2015)	GDS-5
71	Martínez-Velilla et al. (2021)	GDS-15
72	McNeil et al. (1991)	BDI
73	Morris et al. (2017)	CSDD
74	Motamedi et al. (2021)	GDS-15
75	Netz et al. (1994)	GDS-30
76	Niemi et al. (2016)	PHQ-9
77	Nolte et al. (2015)	PHQ-9
78	Pakkala et al. (2008)	CESD-20
79	Parvin et al. (2020)	GDS-15
80	Phansuea et al. (2020)	GDS-30
81	Picelli et al. (2016)	BDI
82	Piroux et al. (2021)	CESD-20
83	Prakhinkit et al. (2014)	GDS-30
84	Ravari et al. (2021)	BDI-II
85	Redwine et al. (2020)	BDI-IA
86	Requena Hernández et al. (2008)	GDS-30
87	Rica et al. (2020)	BDI
88	Rolland et al. (2007)	MADRS
89	Roswiyani et al. (2020)	BDI-II

90	Sahin et al. (2018)	GDS-15
91	Schoene et al. (2015)	PHQ-9
92	Shahidi et al. (2011)	GDS-30
93	Sims et al. (2006)	GDS-30 & CESD-20
94	Sims et al. (2009)	CESD-20
95	Singh et al. (1997a), Singh et al. (1997b)	BDI & GDS-30 & HAMD-17
96	Singh et al. (2005)	HAMD-17 et GDS-30
97	Smart et al. (2012)	CDS
98	Solianik et al. (2021)	HADS
99	Solla et al. (2019)	BDI
100	Swinnen et al. (2021)	CSDD
101	Takahashi et al. (2019)	GDS-15
102	Taylor-Piliae et al. (2014)	CESD-20
103	Teixeira-Machado et al. (2015)	BDI
104	Tekin et al. (2022)	GDS-30
105	Telenius et al. (2015)	CSDD
106	Teri et al. (2003)	CSDD
107	Tollár et al. (2018)	BDI
108	Tollár et al. (2019)	BDI
109	Tremont et al. (2022)	CESD
110	Tsang et al. (2006)	GDS-15
111	Tsang et al. (2013)	GDS-15
112	Tse et al. (2014)	GDS-15
113	Underwood et al. (2013)	GDS-15
114	Vahlberg et al. (2017)	GDS-20
115	Vankova et al. (2014)	GDS-15
116	Villaverde Gutiérrez et al. (2012)	GDS-30
117	Wagg et al. (2019)	CESD-10
118	Wang et al. (2009)	CESD-20
119	Wang et al. (2020)	GDS-15
120	Wi et al. (2013)	GDS-15
121	Williams & Lord (1997)	DASS-21
122	Williams & Tappen (2008)	CSDD
123	Wolf et al. (2001)	HADS
124	Wu et al. (2020)	GDS-15
125	Yi & Yim (2021)	GDS-30
126	Yu et al. (2022)	BDI
127	Zhang et al. (2015)	GDS-30
128	Zheng et al. (2022)	CSDD
129	Zhu et al. (2018)	GDS-15